

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Phenacyl Bromide by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III)

M. KRISHNA PILLAY* and S. M. MAZHAR NAZEEB KHAN

Department of Chemistry, Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirapalli-620 024

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Kinetics of oxidation a few phenacyl bromides in aqueous acetonitrile by hexacyanoferrate(III) at 10°, has been studied. The reaction is first order in oxidant, phenacyl bromide and hydroxide. The enolate of phenacyl bromide and ferricyanide are the reactive species. A suitable mechanism is suggested. Substituent effect is also analysed.

Potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) is an one-electron oxidant with a redox potential of +0.34 eV. Even though it is a weak oxidant, a number of organic compounds has been oxidised by hexacyanoferrate(III) either in the alkaline or acidic medium¹. Metal ion catalysis of oxidation has been also investigated². Comparatively recent reports on the oxidation of acetophenone and fluorene with alkaline hexacyanoferrate^{3,4} prompted us to take up the study of the oxidation of ω -haloarylketones.

Results and Discussion

In the present study, phenacyl bromide was oxidised in 50% aqueous acetonitrile medium by hexacyanoferrate(III) under alkaline condition at low temperature (10°). The optimum conditions (pseudo-first order) for the oxidation study were found to be: $[\text{PhCOCH}_2\text{Br}] = 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] = 0.001 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 0.0075 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{KCl}] = 0.25 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and temperature = 10°. The rates of reaction were investigated

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING $[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$, $[\text{PhCOCH}_2\text{Br}]$, $[\text{KCl}]$, $[\text{NaOH}]$ AND SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON THE SECOND RATE CONSTANT

Temp. = 10°

$[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ M	$[\text{PhCOCH}_2\text{Br}]$ M	$[\text{KCl}]$ M	$[\text{NaOH}]$ M	Solvent Acetonitrile %	$10^{-1} k_2$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
0.000 75	0.01	0.25	0.000 75	50	2.54
0.001	0.01	0.25	0.000 75	50	1.85
0.001 25	0.01	0.25	0.000 75	50	1.06
0.001	0.007 5	0.25	0.000 75	50	2.07
0.001	0.010 0	0.25	0.000 75	50	1.83
0.001	0.012 5	0.25	0.000 75	50	2.16
0.001	0.015	0.25	0.000 75	50	2.04
0.001	0.01	0.25	0.007 5	50	1.83
0.001	0.01	0.20	0.007 5	50	1.70
0.001	0.01	0.15	0.007 5	50	1.17
0.001	0.01	0.10	0.007 5	50	0.81
0.001	0.01	0.25	0.005	50	No reaction
0.001	0.01	0.25	0.007 5	50	2.44
0.001	0.01	0.25	0.010	50	2.33
0.001	0.01	0.25	0.012 5	50	2.26
0.001	0.01	0.25	0.007 5	40	0.90
0.001	0.01	0.25	0.007 5	50	1.85

by keeping one variable changing and keeping other variables constant. The kinetic data are collected and presented in Table 1. The reaction has first-order dependence on sodium hydroxide and hexacyanoferrate(III) concentration (Fig. 1). But contrary to the expectation, the k_0 (observed k) value decreased with increase in the initial concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III). This kind of observation has been reported in the literature⁵. The first order kinetic dependence on hexacyanoferrate(III) concentration implies that a free radical is an intermediate and that a second molecule of hexacyanoferrate(III) reacts in a rapid step after the rate-determining step.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log(a-x)$ vs time-effect of change in $[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$.

The reaction is largely influenced by variation in ionic strength which is a dominant characteristic of ion-ion reactions. There is large increase in the k_0 value when increasing amounts of potassium chloride were added. Increasing the proportion of acetonitrile increases the rate.

Effect of substituents: In the case of substituted phenacyl bromides (Table 2) it was observed that the electron-withdrawing groups in the benzene ring facilitate the oxidation and electron-releasing groups retard the reaction. This observation indicates that the reactions take place via the enolate (which is stabilised by electron-withdrawing groups) as in the case of oxidation of acetophenone.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SUBSTITUENTS

Substrate	10 k_2 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenacyl bromide	2.89
Phenacyl bromide	1.85
<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenacyl bromide	0.88
<i>p</i> -Nitroacetophenone	14.5 ^a
Acetophenone	0.559 ^a
<i>p</i> -Methoxyacetophenone	0.309 ^a

^aValues in 50% aqueous methanol at 30°.

The alkali dependence of the reaction indicates that the phenacyl bromide forms an anion with sodium hydroxide. Decreasing the polarity of the medium increases the rate of the reaction. So the reaction is probably going through a free radical intermediate.

The reaction involves the enolate anion of phenacyl bromide. The reacting species are enolate and ferricyanide anions and a radical is formed from the interaction of these two anions. The oxidation of the enolate anion by hexacyanoferrate(III) occurs by the electron transfer rather than the complex formation as suggested by Speakman and Waters⁶. This radical is rapidly oxidised to form an intermediate which undergoes further oxidation to give the final product. The mechanism is as below. The rate law could be expressed as

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = k_o [\text{Ph}.\text{CO}.\text{CH}_2\text{Br}] [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] [\text{OH}^-]$$

Final product ← Intermediate product

From the above mechanism the rate expression can be written as

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_2\text{Br}] [\text{OH}^-] [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{k_{-1} [\text{H}_2\text{O}] + k_2 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}$$

Experimental

Potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) (AnalaR) was used as such. Acetonitrile was shaken with anhydrous potassium carbonate, kept overnight and distilled after removing potassium carbonate. Phenacyl bromide⁷, *p*-methoxyphenacyl bromide and *p*-nitrophenacyl bromide were prepared by the reported procedures.

The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by allowing an excess of hexacyanoferrate(III) (0.04M) to react with phenacyl bromide (0.01M) under alkaline condition (0.3M) and estimating the unreacted hexacyanoferrate(III) in acid condition after the completion of the reaction. The stoichiometry of the reaction was 1 : 4 between the substrate and oxidant. This is consistent with the following equation.

The product of oxidation was found to be benzoic acid.

Rate measurement: Potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) and sodium hydroxide solutions were prepared by using double-distilled water. The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions, i.e. [substrate] ≫ [oxidant]. The reaction vessel containing hexacyanoferrate(III) solution was wrapped with black cloth. The reactants were kept in nitrogen atmosphere for a few minutes. The solutions were thermostated (±0.01°) at 10° in a water-bath. Equal volumes of solutions were mixed and a portion of the reaction mixture was transferred to a spectrophotometric cell. The reaction was monitored for the disappearance of hexacyanoferrate(III) at 420 nm by using a Carl-Zeiss specard uv-vis spectrophotometer at regular intervals of time. The reaction was followed upto 50%. The pseudo-first order rate constant (k_o) was evaluated using the usual equation.

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